

Non-Trajectory Intervals in Lorentz Invariants and Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 9, 2024

Lorentz transformations act on specific vectors such as (x,ct) and (pc,E) . In the case of (x,ct) it is presumed that one is concerned with a trajectory point rather than a general point in spacetime. In particular, Newtonian mechanics yields $x(t)$ as its key objective. In the case of Lorentz invariants such as $A = -Et+px$, it is again assumed, it seems, that x,ct represents a trajectory point. In other words, in one frame one has E_1,p_1, x_1,t_1 and in another E_2,p_2,t_2,x_2 . Thus, the idea of invariance is taken to be related to considering the same trajectory and (p,E) points in one frame versus another. It is possible to create intervals in one frame using $A_1-A_2 = -Et_1+px_1 - (-Et_2 + px_2)$, but again x_1,t_1 and x_2,t_2 would be considered to be two points on the spacetime trajectory.

In this note, we suggest that given that trajectories contain many spacetime points and may be constantly shifted, it is not fully useful to consider the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ solely in terms of trajectory points. (There is of course no issue with considering such points.) We suggest that given the various shifts and numerous trajectory points there should exist a more general notion of invariance of $A = -Et+px$ in each frame. In other words, this notion of invariance is linked with new physical consequences.

This leads to the notion of removing the frame dependent information in A , namely E and p . One way to do this is to introduce intervals $dt=\text{constant}/E$ and $dx=\text{constant}/p$, something we have noted in previous notes. The point is that one now ignores the notion of a spacetime trajectory altogether and argues for the existence of a fundamental concept of intervals which maintain the invariance of the Lorentz invariant in each frame. This is an idea which exists beyond the notion of a trajectory. This idea of special dt and dx intervals does not exist in classical mechanics. It suggests that invariance in different frames is linked to a new notion of dt, dx intervals which should have physical implications (2-slit experiments etc) and represents quantum mechanical behaviour.

Trajectories

Classical mechanics focuses largely on classical trajectories $x(t)$. In particular, Newton's second law solution leads to a solution of $x(t)$ from a differential equation. (The Lagrangian or Hamiltonian approaches are also based on finding a trajectory.) Even a conservation of energy equation yields $v(x)$ at x or $dx/dt = v(x)$ which may be solved for $x(t)$. Thus, the main focus is on the trajectory.

Special relativity does not eliminate this notion of trajectory, rather it takes an (x,ct) as seen in one frame and translates or maps it to a (x',ct') in a different frame (i.e. the particle seen by a frame moving with constant $-v$). As a result, one would at first expect special relativity to also focus almost entirely on trajectories as well. The various Lorentz invariants which appear and contain x,t would be considered to be restricted to spacetime trajectory points e.g.

$$A = -Et+px \quad \text{with } t,x \text{ being a spacetime trajectory point ((1))}$$

In fact, it does not seem to make physical sense to consider any x, ct points which are not trajectory points. Even if one were to create intervals from ((1)):

$$A1 - A2 = (-Et1 + p x1) - (-E t2 - p x2) \quad ((2))$$

One would assume that $t1, x1$ and $t2, x2$ were points on a trajectory as these are the only points which seem to be physically relevant.

In other words, the notion of trajectory from Newtonian mechanics carries over to special relativity.

The Notion of Invariance in Special Relativity

Even though the idea of a trajectory still holds in special relativity, a Newtonian viewpoint would be to view each frame as its own world with a specific trajectory. In such a case, the Lorentz transformation simply maps an x, ct in one frame to an x', ct' in another. If an observer exists only in one frame, then he/she is not necessarily interested in the variable values (x', ct') of an observer in the second frame. In other words, one does not really focus on the idea of invariance between different frames as a main concept. One is rather interested in a description of a trajectory in terms of a set of numbers in one frame and a corresponding set of numbers describing the same trajectory as seen in the second frame.

We suggest, however, that special relativity introduces a new concept that is not present in Newtonian mechanics, namely the idea of invariance of frames regardless of the numbers describing the trajectory. A trajectory still exists and is certainly relevant and is described by x, ct in one frame and a set of x', ct' in another. Nevertheless, we argue there should exist an independent concept ensuring invariance between all frames. In such a case, each frame is characterized by its p and E values and to have invariance, one must remove this information, as we have argued in previous notes. This leads to the idea of non-trajectory based intervals:

$$dx = \text{constant}/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \text{constant}/E \quad ((2))$$

With the use of these intervals, one removes p and E information from A in each frame without any regard to trajectory. This is a new physical concept not present in Newtonian mechanics, but it has implications which must be borne out experimentally which is what happens in 2-slit interference etc. As a result, the notion of frame invariance seems to introduce a new kind of physics, namely that of intervals dx, dt for each frame based on E and p .

Conservation of Momentum and Energy

The idea of intervals \hbar/p and \hbar/E (constant= \hbar) matches ((2)) leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ if one considers uniform probability within an interval together with the enforcement of the intervals in space and time. This automatically yields a scheme for enforcing energy and momentum conservation, i.e.

Integral dt exp(iE1t) exp(-iE2t) = 0 if E1 not=E2 and Integral dx exp(-ip1x)exp(ip2x) = 0 if p1 not=p2 ((3))

Now, conservation of momentum and energy already exists in Newtonian mechanics without any notion of intervals and exp(-iEt)exp(ipx). The idea of introducing the intervals hbar/p, hbar/E is to introduce a general scheme for invariance between different frames regardless of the specific trajectory.

If one considers uniform probability within each 0 to hbar/p x-unit, one requires a periodic function which marks these x units, but at the same time respects uniform probability within each. No notion of conservation of momentum is introduced at this stage. It is known that the complex number exp(i theta) treats each theta point with uniform probability from 0 to 2*3.14. Thus. exp(ipx) appears to describe a probability which is required, but has the built-in feature that:

$$\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((3))$$

i.e. conservation of momentum. If one has no intervals, i.e. Newtonian mechanics, then spatial probability for any p is 1/L (where L is an arbitrary length) and there is no built-in conservation of momentum from this probability. In the case of a p based interval (required to remove p from -Et+px), one begins with linearity in p. P1+p2 leads to an interval which differs from p3+p4 if p1+p2 not =p3+p4. In order to create these intervals with uniform probability within each, one may consider a periodic function with equally sized crests and troughs. (This function is part of exp(ipx).) In the case of a sin(px), these functions are orthogonal for different p values, e.g. Integral dx sin(p1x)sin(p2x) = 0. In particular, if exp(-i(p1+p2)x) exp(i(p3+p4)x) leads to an exp(i P x), then this integrates to 0 if the range is over a period. In other words, using the overlap exp(-i(p1+p2)x) exp(i(p3+p4)x) either eliminates intervals (if there is a momentum match i.e. momentum conservation) or leads to a periodic function which integrates to 0 over a period and so conservation of momentum is directly related to the interval probability function exp(ipx).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics follows from degeneracy in the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et+px$, i.e. if x_0 , to yield an A value, x_0+hbar/p and t_0+hbar/E yield the same A value. The point we make in this note is that in general, x,t should be a trajectory point in the usual sense of special relativity. In other words, in both Newtonian mechanics and special relativity one is interested in trajectories x(t). Special relativity simply maps an x,t point in one frame to an x',t' in another. It does not destroy the notion of trajectory. We argue, however, that there is a more general notion associated with the invariance of special relativity. Instead of simply considering invariance of $A = -Et+px$ for a given trajectory point in different frames, one may argue for a new physical principle behind the invariance of all frames, ignoring the trajectory so to speak. (This does not mean that a trajectory does not exist, but rather that there is a more general way of considering the notion of invariance in different frames. This new principle is associated with t and x intervals which remove the frame-defining information p,E i.e. $dx= constant/p$ and $dt=constant/E$. This, in turn,

leads to a probability function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ if one wishes to enforce intervals, but have uniform probability within each. Given that the intervals are based on linear E and p functions, this becomes directly linked to conservation of E and p as $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)=\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. The various $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are orthogonal to each other.